

A Study on Role of Customers in Creating a Business Model in Online Banking

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Abstract

In the past few decades, the customer has been silent and hidden such as watching television or listening to lecture. But in present era, the customers do not want to just provide feedback or provide suggestions but also to be a co-designer or co-creator of the products they avail of. The study focuses on appraising customer’s preferences for utilizing services of online banking provided by the banks. The present paper deals with the factors influencing the preference of customers for choosing online banking services. The study examines the customer perception, preference, problems and suggestions about online banking services. The study would help the banks to improve the level of online banking and to know potential issues or services that should be introduced. It would also facilitate the customers to overcome the issues in online banking industry by making the customers as the active co-designer or co-creator- by framing an apt business model for online banking.

Keywords: Online banking, Customer preference, Business model.

Introduction

In the present era, most of the organizations are changing their business operations through internet. These business organizations are adopting the advanced technology through internet facility. . Banks cater to the needs of agriculturists, industrialists, traders and to all the other sections of the society. Thus, they accelerate the economic growth of a country. The increased trend towards electronic delivery of banking products and services is occurring due to a combination of consumer demand and the increasingly competitive environment of the global banking industry. Since it is now possible to render all banking services electronically, with adequate security and at lower costs, many banks now feel the pressure to do business through the Internet. Customers are now demanding more customized products /services on online at a lower price. While the banks in developed

countries use the Internet to operate as banks without a physical location, banks in developing countries are still using the Internet primarily just as an information delivery tool to improve their relationships with their customers.

Review of Literature

According to Ahmad and Al-Zu' bi (2011), security had a significant influence on customer satisfaction. Privacy is another important element which always concerns customers. It is always the customers hope that the banks can protect their personal and financial information especially when they do transactions via online banking.

R. Garg, (2013), examined the customer's perceptions towards internet banking facility and also analyzed the customer's satisfaction with various parameters of internet banking services. In total 180 respondents were surveyed to achieve the objective of the study. The study found that perception of customers towards internet banking service quality was largely influenced by the „reliability', 'user-friendliness', 'responsiveness', 'accuracy', 'speed of service' and 'compatibility'.

According to Hanson & Kalyanam (2007), e-banking has popularized with very fast pace. As people have started using ATMs, the customer visits to bank branches have reduced and it reduced the requirement of bank branches even more when internet banking was introduced to the customers in late 1990s.

Tom E (2001) examined that in addition to previous electronic banking delivery systems-automated teller machine (ATMs) and telephone transaction processing centers, online banking provides banks a new and more efficient electronic delivery tool.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify the factors influencing the customer's preference for online banking services
2. To study the level of satisfaction with online banking service customers.
3. To identify the future expectations of customers for online banking services.

Research Methodology

This study is intended to cover the satisfaction level and future expectations of customers who avail of Online banking services from the banking sectors in virudhunagar town. The data gathered for the study was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The sampling technique used is Simple Random sampling, where the sample size of 90 respondents represents the customers of online banking service. The primary data collected for the study were analyzed with the help of various statistical measures such as simple percentage analysis, Friedman test, ANOVA and Multiple Regression.

Analysis of Data

Table: 1 Respondent's Demographic profile

Variables		No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age of Respondents	upto 25 years	35	39
	between 26-50	42	47
	above 50	13	14
Gender	Male	65	72
	Female	25	28

Educational Qualification	no proper schooling	7	8
	School Level	20	22
	College level	23	26
	Professional	25	28
	Diploma	15	17
Occupation	Student	19	21
	Business	35	39
	Agriculture	10	11
	Employee	26	29

Source: Primary data

From the above table it is clear that 47% of the respondents belong to the age group between 26-50 years, 39% belong to up to 25 years and 14% are in the age group of above 50 years. As specified in above table it is clear that 72% of the respondents are male and 28% of the respondents belong to female group. The survey above table reveals that 7% are Illiterate respondents, 22% are school level educated respondents, 26% are college level respondents, 28% are professional level respondents, and 17% are diploma level respondents. It is also clear that 21% of the respondents' occupational status is studentship, 39% are businessman, 11% carry on agriculture and 29% are salaried employees.

Fried Man Test

The Friedman's test is a non-parametric statistical test developed by the U.S. economist Milton Friedman. The test is a non-parametric alternative to ANOVA with repeated measures. It is used to test for differences between groups when the dependent variable being measured is ordinal.

In this research, Fried man test was used to test the difference between ranks assigned by the customers to their future expectations for online banking.

H0: There is no significant difference in the ranks assigned by the customers to their future expectations towards online banking.

The result of mean ranks and significance in ranking the source of information is given below.

Table: 2 Ranks

	Mean Rank
Reasonable cost	1.26
Security	2.52
Quality of service	3.11
Ease of use of all ages	2.63

The above table shows that reasonable cost is ranked first with mean rank of 1.26; Security and safety of data is ranked second with mean rank of 2.52 followed by ease of use by all ages with third rank having 2.63 as mean rank. Quality of service is ranked fourth with 3.11 mean.

Table: 3 Test Statistics^a

N	90
Chi-Square	5.495
df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.139

a. Friedman Test

The Friedman test was conducted to determine whether the ranks assigned by the customers to their future expectations towards online banking are the same. Results of that analysis indicated that there is a no differential rank ordered for the four attributes in their future expectation, with $\chi^2 = 5.495$ and $p, 0.139 < .05$. Hence, null hypothesis is accepted.

Analysis of Variance

ANOVA technique is used when an independent variable is of nominal scale with more than two categories and the dependent variable is metric or at least on interval scale. In the present study, one-way ANOVA was used to analyze the relationship between customers' different occupation status and factors influencing the usage of online banking.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between customers' occupation status and their importance towards factors influencing the usage of online banking.

Table: 4 ANOVA

Factors		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Time saving	Between Groups	15.192	4	3.798	5.453	.001
	Within Groups	59.208	85	.697		
	Total	74.400	89			
Easy and convenience	Between Groups	32.431	4	8.108	9.913	.000
	Within Groups	69.524	85	.818		
	Total	101.956	89			
Speed	Between Groups	14.742	4	3.686	4.038	.005
	Within Groups	77.580	85	.913		
	Total	92.322	89			
Security	Between Groups	14.441	4	3.610	6.863	.000
	Within Groups	44.714	85	.526		
	Total	59.156	89			
Transparency	Between Groups	27.556	4	6.889	9.934	.000
	Within Groups	58.944	85	.693		
	Total	86.500	89			

At 5% level of significance (95% level of confidence), this analysis does not support the null hypothesis as the 'p' values of all factors are less than the significance value of 0.01. Thus, there is difference in customer's occupation status and their importance towards factors influencing the usage of online banking.

Regression model

Multiple regression analysis is to explain the variation in one variable (called the dependent variable), based on the variation in two or more other variables (called the independent variables). Here the

Dependent variable

Y= Usage of online banking

Independent Variables

- X1 = Age
- X2 = Education
- X3 = Awareness about online services
- X4 = Convenience
- X5 = Web design
- X6 = Service quality

Table: 5 ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.142	1	6.142	4.123
	Residual	384.392	88	1.490	
	Total	390.535	89		

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service Quality, Web designing and content, Convenience, Awareness about online services, age, Education

b. Dependent Variable: Usage of online banking

From ANOVA analysis summary table, the statistical significance of the model is to be proved first. From the above table the p-value 0.043, which is less than 0.05, which means this model is acceptable.

Table: 6 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.787a	.607	.594	.6472

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service Quality, Web designing and content, Convenience, Awareness about online services, age, Education

b. Dependent Variable: Usage of online banking

Multiple regression analysis result of impacts of factors usage of online banking services is revealed in Table. As shown in the model summary, R²=0.607 (adjusted R²=0.594) suggests the explained degree of impact on risk bearing capacity of investors by 6 variables: Age, Education, Awareness about online services, Convenience, Web design and Service quality 60.7%, that is to say, these 6 variables have 60.7% level of influence on usage of online banking services.

Table: 7 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.978	.355		5.574	.000
Age	.528	.081	.000	-.011	.001
Education	.066	.093	.066	.711	.023
Awareness about online services	-.032	.094	-.032	-.347	.043
Web designing and content	-.037	.091	-.032	-.408	.001
Convenience	.026	.082	.022	.320	.000
Service Quality	.120	.074	.109	1.631	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Usage of online banking

The regression model coefficient of impacts of factors on customers online banking service is shown in Table . According to the result of regression coefficient, we built a regression model with non-standardized coefficient. Hence the regression model is:

$$Y = (1.978) + (0.528) \text{ Age} + (0.066) \text{ Education} - (0.032) \text{ Awareness} - (0.037) \text{ Web designing} + (0.026) \text{ Convenience} + (0.120) \text{ Service Quality}$$

One can also note that the t test for the significance of individual independent variables (X1 to X6) indicates that the significance level of 0.05 (confidence level of 95), all these six independent variables are statistically significant in the model. However, of these six variables age is the dominating influencing variable, followed by service quality.

Implication of the Study

1. From the above analysis it is found that 47 % of the respondents are under the age category between 26-50 years and 72% are male customers.
2. Under the category of educational qualification 29% of the respondents are professionals. On the basis of occupation 39% of respondents are business people who use online banking services.
3. From the result of Friedman test there is no significant difference in the ranks assigned by the customers to their future expectations towards online banking.
4. From the result of ANOVA there is no significant difference between customers' occupation status and their importance towards factors influencing the usage of online banking.
5. A model is built using regression and it is found that there is a positive impact by the variables age, education, convenience and service quality towards online banking services. The variables web design and awareness on online banking have a negative impact towards online services.

Suggestions

- The bank should come forward with more meaningful advertisements and awareness campaigns to create awareness among customer's regarding online banking services and to make online banking popular among the entire age and occupation category of people.
- Banks should organize public exhibitions and talk shows and make products accessible to all customers.
- Banks may try to win customers confidence by providing adequate security to transaction, and the technology should be such way that can be utilized by all age category of people.

Conclusion

Since the customers are using online banking nowadays due to its relative advantages over traditional method, the bank should make customers to participate in decision making process while introducing a new business model. The most important factor to be considered in online banking is security, where the information provided by the customer should be kept confidential. Also the bank provides should assure that information will not be misused and their privacy will be respected. Generally, young customers are less risk adverse than the aged customers. So bank must target young customers for the online banking services.

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